

Deliverable No. 2.2

Project acronym:

FarFish

Project title:

Responsive Results-Based Management and capacity building for EU Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement- and international waters

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¹ Document will be a draft until it was approved by the coordinator

² PU: Public, PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services), RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services), CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

³ The initials of the revising individual in capital letters

Deliverable D2.2

Data Management Plan under the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot (Version 3 at M36)

25/05/2020

Executive Summary

The overall goal of WP2 in FarFish is to "*advance knowledge and collate data related to biological characteristics of the main fish stocks in the selected fisheries, and to evaluate the appropriateness, relevance and applicability of stock assessment models currently in use for these fisheries*", as per the DoA.

Task 2.2 and deliverable 2.2 contributes towards these goals by creating a "*Data Management Plan*", as per the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data Pilot. The deliverable contains 39 forms detailing the content of all datasets used within FarFish, how it will be preserved, and steps taken to make data publically available after the project end.

The Data Management Plan is a "living document" that is to be updated regularly throughout the project. The first version was published in month 6 of the project, a second version was published in month 18, and this third version is now published in month 36. The final version will be published at project end.

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1 Revision history

Version	Date	Revised by	Comment
V0.1	08.11.2017	PBS	Draft deliverable
V1.0	29.11.2017	PBS	Completed deliverable
V2.0	28.11.2018	PBS	M18 Periodic update <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Added 22 new forms – no updates to existing forms • Updated the format for all existing forms
V3.0	25.05.2020	PBS	M36 Periodic update <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One new form added (p.47) • Minor revision to certain forms (time period covered (p. 9/10/46) and dataset owner (p. 15))

2 Introduction

Over the course of a research project, considerable amounts of data are gathered. Often, these data are not preserved or made available for reuse later on, causing time and effort to be spent in other projects gathering similar data. The goal of the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data Pilot is remedy this issue, by ensuring that research data generated through a project is made available for reuse after a projects end. The H2020 Open Research Data Pilot is based on the principle of making data FAIR:

- Findable
- Accessible
- Interoperable
- Reusable

As a way of managing the data used during a project lifetime, a Data Management Plan (DMP) must be created. The DMP-forms includes details on:

- the handling of research data during and after the end of the project
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- which methodology and standards will be applied
- whether data will be shared/made open access
- how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project)
- ethical issues related to the data
- estimated costs associated with data archiving/sharing

The creation of the DMP is the responsibility of task 2.2/deliverable 2.2. As per the DoA, task 2.2 will fulfill three requirements as a participant in the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot: *"Firstly, the collected research data should be deposited in data repository (...). Secondly, the project will have to take measures to enable third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate this research data. Finally, a Data Management Plan (DMP) has to be developed detailing what kind of data the project is*

expected to generate, whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and reuse, and how it will be curated and preserved".

The Data Management Plan is a “living document” that is to be updated regularly throughout the project. The first version was published in month 6 of the project, a second version was published in month 18, and this third version is now published in month 36. The final version will be published at project end.

3 Method

In order to collect information from the project participants, a form and an explanation describing the desired content of each DMP-component was sent out to all partners by email (both are attached in "Appendix 2 – Templates". Detailed instructions on how to fill out the form was included in the accompanying e-mail. Both the form and the explanation were based on the proposed DMP-structure in "Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020" (2016). Along with the two forms, an example from a previous project was distributed in the same email.

In order to harmonize the forms, the formatting of certain forms have been edited where needed. No changes have ben made to the content.

4 Conclusion

The deliverable contains 39 forms, detailing the content of the different datasets, the ways in which data will be stored and how/if it will be made available at the project end. The forms are grouped according to case study. Datasets not pertaining to one individual case study are grouped in a separate category: "Non-case study specific". If no case study-specific datasets have been submitted for a particular case study, the case study is not included in the list in the appendix.

During the later stages of the project, relevant datasets will be uploaded to the FarFish Database (FFDB), created as part of task 6.1 in Work Package 6 "Development of management tools" as a means of storing research data. The FFDB will be accessible from the FarFish webpage. At- or near the project end, datasets will be uploaded from the FFDB to OpenAire. A FarFish account has been created on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/farfish2020?page=1&size=20>). Most datasets can be made publically available, with the exception of meeting minutes and reports from the Joint Committee meetings. A full review of what data can, and should, be made available will be made nearer the project end.

With the exception of personal information collected during interviews, the potential for ethical issues raised by FarFish are relatively minor, though this might vary from dataset to dataset. Participation in the project is on a voluntarily basis, and participants have the right to limit the use of any information they provide and may request that information collected is deleted at the end of the project. FarFish follows the Eurostat rules and national guidelines on data confidentiality, and the ICC/ESOMAR International Code on Market, Opinion and Social Research and Data Analytics. See the "Ethics and Security" section in the DoA for more information.

The DMP is intended to be a "living" document, and will evolve as the project progresses. Periodic revisions of the DMP are planned once within each 18-month periodic reporting period. Ahead of each periodic review, an email will be sent out to all project participants, asking them to update the DMP-forms pertaining to their datasets by either editing existing information or by adding new forms if necessary.

Extra revisions might be scheduled should it be needed. The table in chapter 0 "Revision history" provides a summary of revisions carried out over the lifetime of this Data Management Plan. It provides a version number, the date of the latest revision, the initials of the editor, and a comment describing the changes made.

5 Acknowledgements

We wish to acknowledge the contribution of all project participants who contributed to the completion of this deliverable.

6 References

- "*Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020*" – EC Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, version 3.0, July 26th 2016
- "*Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020*" – EC Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, version 3.1, August 25th 2016
- "*OpenAire: What is the Open Research Data Pilot*" – Accessed 31.10.2017:
<https://www.openaire.eu/what-is-the-open-research-data-pilot>.

7 Appendix

7.1 Appendix 1: Data management plans

7.1.1 Seychelles

1. Data set reference/name	<i>IndustrialPS_Processed_0016: Purse Seine Fishery – Seychelles – Fishing vessels, Catch, effort, Length frequency, 2000-2019</i> SFA
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The purse seine fishery datasets contain information on all purse seiners (including EU vessels) licensed to operate within the Seychelles EEZ. Data are collected on vessels, catch by species, effort, geographical fishing area, length frequency, landing and transshipment. The data is gathered for scientific analysis, management and policy decision making purposes, for access payment and to meet obligations to international bodies (e.g IOTC, FAO etc) Data is collected from Fishing vessels (logbook), vessel agents (landing/transshipment), SFA technicians (length frequency) and is captured, processed and managed by the Seychelles Fishing Authority.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The described sources uses standard nomenclature for statistical data as per SWIOFP Statbase metadata format. Data can be extracted from MS Access database into Excel- and CSV files A PDF report based on the data is available for download at http://www.sfa.sc/publication.jsp
3.2 Making data openly accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project- generated data will be shared in designated publication at the Flag level but not at individual vessel level for confidentiality reasons. Data are also available in public domain on IOTC website www.iotc.org Data not publicly available may be provided upon an official request. Data can be extracted from Ms Access and provided in requested format. Metadata is available in Ms Excel format
3.3 Making data interoperable	Data are interoperable. Metadata vocabularies are as per SWIOFP Statbase project.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Published data will be re-usable. Confidential data will be assessed on a case by case basis upon official request.
4. Allocation of resources	
5. Data security	Data reside on a secure server and is backed-up on a regularly basis.
6. Ethical aspects	
7. Other	SFA works in collaboration with our partners Institut de Recherche pour le Development (IRD)- France and Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO) for data management.

1. Data set reference/name	<i>IndustrialSV_Data_0016: Supply Vessel – Seychelles – Fishing vessels and effort 2005-2018</i> SFA
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Supply vessel dataset contain information on all supply vessel in the purse seine fishery (including EU vessels) licensed to operate within the Seychelles EEZ. Data are collected on vessels, effort and geographical operation area. • The data is gathered for management and policy decision making purposes, for scientific analysis and to meet obligations to international bodies (e.g IOTC, FAO etc) • Data is collected from Fishing vessels (logbook) and is captured, processed and managed by the Seychelles Fishing Authority.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The described sources use standard nomenclature for statistical data as per SWIOFP Statbase metadata format. • Data can be extracted from MS Access database into Excel files and CSV files • A PDF report based on the data is available for download at http://www.sfa.sc/publication.jsp
3.2 Making data openly accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project- generated data will be shared in designated publication at the Flag level but not at individual vessel level for confidentiality reasons. • Data are also available in public domain on IOTC website www.iotc.org • Data not publicly available may be provided upon an official request. • Data can be extracted from Ms Access and provided in requested format. • Metadata is available in Ms Excel format
3.3 Making data interoperable	Data are interoperable Metadata vocabularies are as per SWIOFP Statbase project
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Published data will be re-usable Confidential data will be assessed on a case by case basis upon official request.
4. Allocation of resources	
5. Data security	Data reside on a secure server and is backed-up on a regularly basis
6. Ethical aspects	
7. Other	SFA works in collaboration with our partners Institut de Recherche pour le Development (IRD)- France and Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO) for data management.

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA, held in Victoria 30 June – 1 July 2016</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA in 2016
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA, held in Brussels 3-4 May 2017.</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA in 2017
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
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3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA, held in Brussels 3-4 May 2017.</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA in 2017
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
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4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA, held in Brussels 10 February 2015.</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA in 2018
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

7.1.2 Senegal

Data set reference and name	<i>Black hakes Merluccius senegalensis and M. polli scientific data surveys 2002-2016</i> COREWAM/CRODT-ISRA
Data set summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The database consists of Senegalese black hakes <i>Merluccius senegalensis</i> and <i>M. polli</i> information originating from 8 scientific deep demersal surveys off Senegal between 2002 and 2016. • It's the first time for black hakes to be namely specified in such fisheries agreement between Senegal and other countries • Spanish and local fleets activities from the end of 1980's to 2016, bearing in mind that hake fisheries are irregularly performed by these fleets. E.g., due to failing of CPUE, there was a break from 2006 to 2014 • Artisanal canoes activities are anecdotic due to their low level catches
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific surveys and industrial data will be openly available. • Black hakes data will be extracted exclusively for that purpose from scientific surveys. Variables and related explanation will be furnished for a better understanding and appropriation of data.
Making data openly accessible	The data will be exchangeable between researchers. It will be in a suitable excel file sheet.
Making data interoperable	The data will reusable during the duration of the Farfish Project.
Data security	Data exist in CRODT/ISRA and are saved within different supports for a long term conservation.
Ethical aspects	Data are Senegalese property. They can be used under scientific authorisation from CRODT/ISRA in the context of FarFish.
Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<p><i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Senegalese SFPA, held in Dakar 15-17 April 2015</i></p> <p><i>(ACCORD DE PARTENARIAT DANS LE DOMAINE DE LA PECHE DURABLE ENTRE L'UNION EUROPEENNE ET LA REPUBLIQUE DU SENEGAL - liere session ordinaire de la Commission mixte – PROCESVERBAL)</i></p> <p>MATIS</p>
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Senegalese SFPA in 2015
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<p><i>List of financial support from EU to Senegal in 2014-2019 in connection with the SFPA and allocation to tasks.</i> <i>(APP Union européenne - Sénégal 2014-2019 MATRICE appui sectoriel)</i></p> <p>MATIS</p>
2. Data summary	List of financial support from EU to Senegal in 2014-2019 in connection with the SFPA and allocation to tasks.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data is in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The data set is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the data might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The data is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<p><i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Senegalese SFPA, held in Brussels 19-29 April 2016</i></p> <p><i>(ACCORD DE PARTENARIAT DANS LE DOMAINE DE LA PECHE DURABLE ENTRE L'UNION EUROPEENNE ET LA REPUBLIQUE DU SENEGAL - 2N^ome session ordinaire de la Commission mixte - Bruxelles, 19-21 Avril 2016 - PROCES VERBAL)</i></p> <p>MATIS</p>
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Senegalese SFPA in 2016
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<p><i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Senegalese SFPA, held in Dakar 10-12 April 2017.</i></p> <p><i>(ACCORD DE PARTENARIAT DANS LE DOMAINE DE LA PECHE DURABLE ENTRE L'UNION EUROPEENNE ET LA REPUBLIQUE DU SENEGAL - 3ieme session ordinaire de la Commission mixte - Dakar, 10-12 Avril 2017 - PROCES VERBAL)</i></p> <p>MATIS</p>
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Senegalese SFPA in 2017
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<p><i>Report of the joint committee for the Senegalese SFPA 2018.</i> <i>(Rapport de la réunion annuelle du Comité Scientifique Conjoint relatif à l'Accord de pêche signé entre la République du Sénégal et l'Union européenne - Dakar, 11-13 juillet 2018 -)</i></p> <p>MATIS</p>
2. Data summary	Report of the joint committee for the Senegalese SFPA 2018.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The report is in pdf format and has been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The report is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the report might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The report is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<p><i>Report of the joint committee for the Senegalese SFPA 2016.</i> <i>(Rapport de la réunion annuelle du Comité Scientifique Conjoint relatif à l'Accord de pêche signé entre la République du Sénégal et l'Union européenne – Dakar, 29 février- 01 & 02 mars 2016)</i></p> <p>MATIS</p>
2. Data summary	Report of the joint committee for the Senegalese SFPA 2016.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The report is in pdf format and has been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The report is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the report might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The report is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<p><i>Report of the joint committee for the Senegalese SFPA 2017.</i> <i>(Rapport de la réunion annuelle du Comité Scientifique Conjoint relatif à l'Accord de pêche signé entre la République du Sénégal et l'Union européenne – Madrid , 09-11 octobre 2017).</i></p> <p>MATIS</p>
2. Data summary	Report of the joint committee for the Senegalese SFPA 2017.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The report is in pdf format and has been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The report is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the report might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The report is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

7.1.3 Mauritania

1. Data set reference/name	<p><i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Mauritanian SFPA, held in Brussels 30-31 May 2016</i></p> <p><i>(ACCORD DE PARTENARIAT DANS LE SECTEUR DE LA PECHE ENTRE LA REPUBLIQUE ISLAMIQUE DE MAURITANIE ET L'UNION EUROPEENNE - PROTOCOLE 2015-2019 - Procès-verbal de la Commission mixte - Tenue à Bruxelles les 30-31 mai 2016)</i></p> <p>MATIS</p>
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Mauritanian SFPA in 2016
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<p><i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Mauritanian SFPA, held in Brussels 20-22 September 2017.</i></p> <p><i>(ACCORD DE PARTENARIAT DANS LE SECTEUR DE LA PECHE ENTRE LA REPUBLIQUE ISLAMIQUE DE MAURITANIE ET L'UNION EUROPEENNE - PROTOCOLE 2015-2019 - Procès-verbal de la Commission mixte - Tenue à Bruxelles les 20, 21 et 22 septembre 2017)</i></p> <p>MATIS</p>
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Mauritanian SFPA in 2017
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Report of the joint committee for the Mauritanian SFPA, for the period 2008-2012; 2013-2014 and 2015-2019. Report published in September 2017. (Rapport conjoint d'exécution et de programmation des Appuis sectoriels 2008-2012; 2013-2014 et 2015-2019)</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Report of the joint committee for the Mauritanian SFPA, for the period 2008-2012; 2013-2014 and 2015-2019
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The report is in pdf format and has been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The report is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the report might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The report is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<p><i>Report of the joint committee for the Mauritanian SFPA 2016.</i> <i>(Rapport de la Réunion annuelle du Comité Scientifique Conjointe relatif à l'Accord de pêche signé entre la République islamique de Mauritanie et l'Union européenne - – Nouakchott, 05 au 07 septembre 2016)</i></p> <p>MATIS</p>
2. Data summary	Report of the joint committee for the Mauritanian SFPA 2016.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The report is in pdf format and has been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The report is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the report might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The report is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<p><i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Mauritanian SFPA, held in Nouakchott 15-16 November 2016.</i> <i>(ACCORD DE PARTENARIAT DANS LE SECTEUR DE LA PECHE ENTRE LA REPUBLIQUE ISLAMIQUE DE MAURITANIE ET L'UNION EUROPEENNE - PROTOCOLE 2015-2019 - Procès-verbal de la Commission mixte extraordinaire - Tenue à Nouakchott les 15-16 novembre 2016)</i></p> <p>MATIS</p>
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Mauritanian SFPA in 2016
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<p><i>Report of the joint committee for the Mauritanian SFPA 2017.</i> <i>(Rapport de la Réunion annuelle du Comité Scientifique Conjoint relatif à l'Accord de pêche signé entre la République islamique de Mauritanie et l'Union européenne Santa Cruz de Tenerife - 03 au 05 octobre 2017 -)</i></p> <p>MATIS</p>
2. Data summary	Report of the joint committee for the Mauritanian SFPA 2017.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The report is in pdf format and has been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The report is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the report might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The report is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

7.1.4 Cabo Verde

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPA, held in Brussels 12 October 2018. (Accord de Partenariat de Peche Durable entre l'Union Européenne et Cabo Verde PROTOCOLE 2014-2018 COMMISSION MIXTE - BRUXELLES, 12 OCTOBRE 2018)</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPA in 2018
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<p><i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPa, held in Brussels 23-25 March 2015.</i></p> <p><i>(ACCORD DE PARTENARIAT DANS LE SECTEUR DE LA PECHE ENTRE L'UNION EUROPEENNE ET LA REPUBLIQUE DU CAP VERT PROTOCOLE 2014-2018 COMMISSION MIXTE - BRUXELLES, 23-25 MARS 2015 - PROCES VERBAL)</i></p> <p>MATIS</p>
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPa in 2015.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<p><i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPA, held in Brussels 28-29 November 2017.</i></p> <p><i>(Accord de Partenariat de Peche Durable NTRE L'UNION EUROPEENNE ET LE CABO VERDE</i></p> <p><i>PROTOCOLE 2014-2018 COMMISSION MIXTE - BRUXELLES, 28-29 NOVEMBRE 2017- PROCES VERBAL)</i></p> <p>MATIS</p>
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPA in 2017.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<p><i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPa, held in Mindelo 11-13 May 2016.</i></p> <p><i>(ACCORD DE PARTENARIAT DANS LE SECTEUR DE LA PECHE ENTRE L'UNION EUROPEENNE ET LA REPUBLIQUE DU CABO VERDE PROTOCOLE 2014-2018 COMMISSION MIXTE - MINDELO, 11-13 MAI 2016- PROCES VERBAL)</i></p> <p>MATIS</p>
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPa in 2016.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

7.1.6 South-East Atlantic

1. Data set reference/name	<i>REPORT OF THE 12th SEAFO SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE</i> IMR
2. Data summary	Report of the 12 th SEAFO Scientific Committee. The report contains meeting agenda/minutes from the 12 th SEAFO Scientific Committee Meeting, as well as tables/reports on catch, stock status, landings, discard and bycatch.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The report can be downloaded directly from the link: http://www.seafo.org/media/4ca98f5f-c111-4bcf-875b-36ac3213b8b7/SEAFOweb/pdf/SC/open/eng/SC%20Report%202016.pdf . Other reports can be accessed at the SEAFO web site: http://www.seafo.org/Documents .
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data is openly accessible.
3.3 Making data interoperable	The report on the 12 th SEAFO Scientific Committee is available in PDF-format, as are other reports which can be access from the SEAFO website http://www.seafo.org/Documents . All reports are available in English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	
4. Allocation of resources	Not applicable.
5. Data security	Data reside on a secure server and is backed-up on a regularly basis.
6. Ethical aspects	Not applicable.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>REPORT OF THE 12th SEAFO SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE</i> IMR
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The dataset contains information on all data gathered for management and policy decision making purposes, for scientific analysis and to meet obligations to international bodies. • Data is collected from Fishing vessels (logbook) and is captured, processed and managed by the SEAFO.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	A PDF report based on the data is available for download at http://www.seafo.org/media/4ca98f5f-c111-4bcf-875b-36ac3213b8b7/SEAFOweb/pdf/SC/open/eng/SC%20Report%202016_pdf
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data is openly accessible.
3.3 Making data interoperable	
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Published data will be re-usable
4. Allocation of resources	Not applicable.
5. Data security	Data reside on a secure server and is backed-up on a regularly basis.
6. Ethical aspects	Not applicable.
7. Other	

7.1.7 Non-case study specific

1. Data set reference/name	FAO - Fisheries and aquaculture software. FishStatJ - software for fishery statistical time series 1950 - 2015. In: FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Department [online]. Syntesa
2. Data summary	The FAO Capture, Aquaculture and Global production databases have been updated with an additional year and now include data from 1950 to 2015. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global Statistical Collections • Regional Capture Statistical Collections • Records Collections • Fact Sheet Collections • Maps Collections
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	FAO ensures quality assurance by documenting each collection to highlight definitions and to specify the structure, sources, coverage, processes, intended use, etc. This is complemented with the <i>CWP Handbook of Fishery Statistical Standards</i> which includes comprehensive definitions of concepts and details of standard classifications. Available at: http://www.fao.org/fishery/cwp/search/en
3.2 Making data openly accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data is available to the public. • Data is available online in a searchable database. No login required. • The website and data sets are available in various languages FAO promotes public access of data at: http://www.fao.org/fishery/statistics/en
3.3 Making data interoperable	All data produced for the project will be delivered and circulated among partners and stakeholders according to the project's guidelines.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	All data collections, also fully-documented, are organized by records, Fact Sheets and maps, thus complementing the overall statistical collections
4. Allocation of resources	Not yet defined
5. Data security	Security of original databases is operated by FAO. Collections and data produced for the project will be storage in the data server belonging to Syntesa. The data produced for the project FarFish will be stored for a period of 10 years after project's completion.
6. Ethical aspects	All copyrights and authorship will be attributed according to academic rigor and integrity
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Eurostat > Fisheries data</i> Syntesa
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fishery statistics are derived from official national sources either directly by Eurostat for the EEA member countries. • The data are collected using internationally agreed concepts and definitions developed by the Coordinating Working Party on Fishery Statistics, comprising Eurostat and several other international organisations with responsibilities in fishery statistics. • The domain "Fisheries" contains data on catches by fishing region, on aquaculture production, on total production, on landings in EEA ports, on trade in fishery products, on the EEA fishing fleet.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical glossary, data and metadata are available online Metadata is available at: http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/metadata Additional guidelines are available at: http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Category:Fisheries
3.2 Making data openly accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data is available to the public. • Data is available online in a searchable database. No login required. • The website and data sets are available in various languages Eurostat has a policy of encouraging free re-use of its data, both for non-commercial and commercial purposes. http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/fisheries/data/database
3.3 Making data interoperable	All data produced for the project will be delivered and circulated among partners and stakeholders according to the project's guidelines
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	All statistical data, metadata, content of web pages or other dissemination tools, official publications and other documents published on its website, with exceptions, can be reused without any payment or written licence provided that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the source is indicated as Eurostat; • when re-use involves modifications to the data or text, this must be stated clearly to the end user of the information.
4. Allocation of resources	Not yet defined
5. Data security	Security of original databases is operated by EUROSTAT. Collections and data produced for the project will be storage in the data server belonging to Syntesa. The data produced for the project FarFish will be stored for a period of 10 years after project's completion.
6. Ethical aspects	All copyrights and authorship will be attributed according to academic rigor and integrity. The basis for the copyright and licence policy of Eurostat is the legal notice of the European Commission Europa website, which can be found here: https://ec.europa.eu/info/legal-notice_en
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) > Economic Analysis (fleet, processing, aquaculture)</i> Syntesa
2. Data summary	Reports referring to topics such as the economic reports on the profitability of EU fleets, the fish-processing sector, etc. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Aquaculture • Fisheries Dependent Information • Fleet Economic Performance • Fish Processing Industry
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	All databases are available online. Metadata is available for each selected database.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data is available to the public. • Data is available online in a searchable database. No login required. • The website and data sets are available in various languages https://stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu/reports/economic
3.3 Making data interoperable	All data produced for the project will be delivered and circulated among partners and stakeholders according to the project's guidelines
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Accompanying each data series, are references to the relevant reports of the STECF where the same data are also published (https://stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu/data-reports). Documentation on the data variables and their definitions together with a publication date are also provided.
4. Allocation of resources	Not yet defined
5. Data security	Security of original databases is operated by STECF and the European Commission Collections and data produced for the project will be storage in the data server belonging to Syntesa. The data produced for the project FarFish will be stored for a period of 10 years after project's completion.
6. Ethical aspects	All copyrights and authorship will be attributed according to academic rigor and integrity. STECF states that the data are made available in the interests of transparency and can be freely used for further analyses provided the source is acknowledged, according to disclaimer available at: https://stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu/data-dissemination
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tuna - ICCAT statistical databases</i> Syntesa
2. Data summary	<p>ICCAT statistical databases are divided in tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task I data include nominal annual catch by species, region, gear, flag, and where possible, separated between EEZ and High Seas. Responsibility for reporting catch and landings data rests on flag states. • Task II data includes Catch and fishing effort statistics for each species by small area (1x1 degree squares for most gears, 5x5 degree squares for longlines), gear, flag, and month. Task II data also include actual size frequencies of samples measured for each species by small area, gear, flag and month.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Most databases currently used in the stock assessments and other SCRS work are of public domain and are published on http://www.iccat.int/en/accesingdb.htm . Metadata is not available
3.2 Making data openly accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data is available online in a searchable database. No login required. • The website and data sets are available in English, French and Spanish. <p>http://www.iccat.int/en/accesingdb.htm</p> <p>The dissemination of ICCAT data is according to the Rules and Procedures for the protection, access to, and dissemination of data compiled by ICCAT, adopted by the Commission in 2010. Available at http://www.iccat.int/Data/REP_EN_10-11 I 1 Annex 6 Confidentiality.pdf.</p>
3.3 Making data interoperable	All data produced for the project will be delivered and circulated among partners and stakeholders according to the project's guidelines
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Additional data clarification is available for Task II data at http://www.iccat.int/Data/t2ce-ENG.pdf and http://www.iccat.int/Data/t2ce-ENG.pdf
4. Allocation of resources	Not yet defined
5. Data security	<p>Security of original databases is operated by ICAAT</p> <p>Collections and data produced for the project will be storage in the data server belonging to Syntesa.</p> <p>The data produced for the project FarFish will be stored for a period of 10 years after project's completion.</p>
6. Ethical aspects	<p>All copyrights and authorship will be attributed according to academic rigor and integrity.</p> <p>Most databases currently used in the stock assessments and other SCRS work are of public domain, dissemination rules include procedures for using data classified as confidential. Available at http://www.iccat.int/Data/REP_EN_10-11 I 1 Annex 6 Confidentiality.pdf.</p>
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Fish_capture_production_all countries: FAO, volume and value</i> Nofima
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This database contains capture production statistics by country or territory, species item, and FAO Major Fishing Area. • Information on capture production is collected annually from relevant national offices concerned with fishery statistics, by means of a system of standardized forms, which list for each country the relative species items and fishing areas breakdown. • In the case of some "aquatic products", data are also obtained from trade associations or other specialized international organizations to which data are also submitted. In this way the statistics are reviewed by subject matter specialists. • Data concerning the nominal catch of certain major groups are generally reviewed in collaboration with the regional agency concerned. For example, for ISSCAAP group 36 (Tunas, bonitos and billfishes) data provided by the national correspondents are often replaced by the "best scientific estimates" produced by regional bodies collecting tuna catch statistics (i.e. ICCAT, IOTC, SPC and IATTC.)
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>Metadata are available at http://www.fao.org/fishery/statistics/global-capture-production/3/en. At present the database shows annual figures for the period from 1950 organized by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - about 240 countries, territories or land areas; - 26 major fishing areas; - approximately 1600 species items (freshwater, brackishwater and marine species of fish, crustaceans, molluscs and other aquatic animals and plants) classified into the FAO International Standard Statistical Classification of Aquatic Animals and Plants (ISSCAAP) <p>Data Periodicity: Data are reported yearly and the period used is the calendar year (1 January - 31 December.) Some countries or areas use a split-year in their reporting (e.g. year ending 30 June.)</p>
3.2 Making data openly accessible	<p>The capture production datasets can be downloaded at the FAO domain, and filtered and viewed by installing the FishStat software: http://www.fao.org/fishery/statistics/software/fishstatj/en</p>
3.3 Making data interoperable	<p>Data are interoperable. More info on standardization and aggregation here: http://www.fao.org/fishery/statistics/global-capture-production/3/en</p>
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	<p>Data are public. No login required. See FAO guidelines on data reuse.</p>
4. Allocation of resources	No additional costs required.
5. Data security	Data are hosted online by FAO, and follows FAO guidelines for data security.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Fish_Trade_EU: Trade – All Member States – import and export, volumes and values, fish products, 2008 – 2018</i> Nofima
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Import to and export from EU Member state per HS code (product ID), reporting and partner country. Both Intra-EU and Extra-EU are relevant. • Intra-EU trade statistics record the movement of goods between Member States. Extra-EU trade statistics record goods imported and exported by the EU from and to non-EU countries. • Intra-EU data is collected from traders, and is closely interlinked with the VAT system. • Extra-EU data on trade in goods with non-EU countries are collected by customs authorities and are based on the records of trade transactions in customs declarations. Extra-EU trade statistics do not cover goods declared orally to customs authorities which are non-commercial, or which are of a commercial nature but have a value not exceeding the statistical threshold of EUR 1 000 and 1 000 kg.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International trade in goods statistics are available in a number of formats (csv, excel, html, PDF, tsv etc.) from the Bulk Download web page (link) and the Easy Comext domain (link). • Metadata (classifications, data availability, etc.) and methodological notes accompany the datasets. • The Easy Comext domain provides access not only to both recent and historical data of the EU and its individual Member States but also to statistics of a significant number of non-EU countries.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Easy Comext is publicly available at http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/newxtweb/ or through an internet search for 'Easy Comext'. The Easy Comext User Manual explains step-by-step how to make a data extraction.
3.3 Making data interoperable	The data is interoperable. The products are classified through Harmonized System Codes - HS (2,4 & 6) and the Combined Nomenclature CN8-codes.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The data is publicly available for all. No login required. Provisions regarding data reuse is specified through Eurostat guidelines (http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/about/policies/copyright).
4. Allocation of resources	No additional costs required.
5. Data security	Data are hosted by Eurostat and follows Eurostat guidelines for data security.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects. See Commissions regulations for data confidentiality http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/research-methodology/statistical-confidentiality .
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>DG MARE – SFP A Evaluation reports</i> Nofima
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ex-post/ex-ante evaluation reports of the SFP A agreements contains a review of the country background, fisheries sector (important fisheries, economic figures, employment, governing bodies), whether the agreements are suited to achieve the goals set, and recommendations for future protocols. • The reports are based on information gathered from various sources (e.g. EU departments and executive agencies, EU-member states administrative bodies, professional association groupings, regional associations, etc).
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Reports are in PDF-format and are available in a searchable database: https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/documentation/studies .
3.2 Making data openly accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The reports are openly accessible and available to the public in a searchable database. No login is required, nor are there any regional lockout mechanisms. • The website is available in all EU-partners' languages. • The reports are available in either English or French. For reports in French only, an English summary is presented.
3.3 Making data interoperable	All data collected during the course of farFish will be circulated among partners and stakeholders according to FarFish guidelines.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Re-use of content is authorised provided the source is acknowledged, and follows the Commissions reuse policy as defined in " <i>Commission Decision of 12 December 2011 on the reuse of Commission documents</i> " http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2011:330:0039:0042:EN:PDF (available in English).
4. Allocation of resources	No additional costs required.
5. Data security	Reports are available on an EU-hosted website, and follows EUs guidelines for data security.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Model outputs an indicators – Data summary, estimates and projections</i> CSIC
2. Data summary	Data provided by model outputs could be a summary of the data available, reference points, indicators (as the estimated TAC value), biomass estimates or forward projections.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Relevant datasets will be uploaded to the FFDB according to the protocol described in D6.1, with keywords referring to the species, location and type of the data (could be a summary of the data available, reference points, biomass estimates or forward projections).
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data sets, e.g. spreadsheets files, will be published on the website https://www.farfish.eu as part of the data management plan (DMP). Wordpress will be used to ensure these are available for other users and search-able through the website.
3.3 Making data interoperable	Project-generated data will be shared in the web https://www.farfish.eu . Original data sources will be regularly updated/alterd in light of new data/corrections. The Data base allows transformation into txt. xls and csv files to favour an easy interaction.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Data will be deposited on the Farfish website. Data will be stored for an indefinite time.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required,
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of Farfish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Historical Fisheries data – Catches/survey time series</i> CSIC
2. Data summary	Historical fisheries data could be catches time series or survey time series. The data could be obtained from international databases and research centers as well as from scientific publications.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Relevant datasets will be uploaded to the FFDB according to the protocol described in D6.1, with keywords referring to the species, location and type of the data (could be mainly catches time series or surveys time series).
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data sets, e.g. spreadsheets files, will be published on the website https://www.farfish.eu as part of the data management plan (DMP). Wordpress will be used to ensure these are available for other users and search-able through the website. No known restrictions yet.
3.3 Making data interoperable	Project-generated data will be shared in the website (if possible) or in designated scientific publications. Original data sources will be regularly updated/changed in light of new data/corrections. The Database allows transformation into txt. xls and csv files to favour an easy interaction.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Data will be deposited on the Farfish website (with password provided to Farfish members if the data set has some legal conflict). Data will be stored for an indefinite time.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of Farfish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Biological fisheries data – Maturity, growth, mortality</i> CSIC
2. Data summary	Data regarding biological aspects of the fisheries can include maturity, growth, mortality and life cycle relevant aspects. The data can be obtained from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - International Databases - Marine research institutes - Oceanographic research centers
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Relevant datasets will be uploaded to the FFDB according to the protocol described in D6.1, with keywords referring to the species, location and type of the data (could be maturity, growth, mortality and life cycle relevant aspects).
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The described sources utilize the standard nomenclature for statistical data. Data sets, e.g. spreadsheets files, will be published on the website https://www.farfish.eu as part of the data management plan (DMP). Wordpress will be used to ensure these are available for other users and search-able through the website. No known restrictions yet.
3.3 Making data interoperable	Project-generated data will be shared in the website (if possible) or in designated scientific publications. Original data sources will be regularly updated/alterd in light of new data/corrections. The Database allows transformation into txt. xls and csv files to favour an easy interaction.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Data will be deposited on the Farfish website (with password provided to Farfish members if the data set has some legal conflict). Data will be stored for an indefinite time.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of Farfish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Decision Support and visualisation tools outputs</i> CSIC
2. Data summary	Could be a summary of the meetings conclusions, surveys results, preference measures given by stakeholders on different options or a summary of model inputs and outputs.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Relevant datasets will be uploaded to the FFDB according to the protocol described in D6.1, with keywords referring to the species, location, type of the data and type of DST used.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data sets, e.g. spreadsheets files, will be published on the website https://www.farfish.eu as part of the data management plan (DMP). Wordpress will be used to ensure these are available for other users and search-able through the website.
3.3 Making data interoperable	Project-generated data will be shared in the web https://www.farfish.eu Original data sources will be regularly updated/alterd in light of new data/corrections. The Data base allows transformation into txt. xls and csv files to favour an easy interaction.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Data will be deposited on the Farfish website. Data will be stored for an indefinite time.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of Farfish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Catch reports by EU vessels in the SFPAs of Seychelles, Mauritania, Cabo Verde and Senegal in 2014-2019</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Catch reports in pdf from an excel sheet.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data is in pdf format and has been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The report is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The report is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Catch reports by EU vessels in non-EU waters in 2014-2019</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Excel sheet containing detailed catch and landing reports that show by fishing vessel, species and fishing trip information on MS registration of vessel, registration nr. of vessel, month of fishing trip, fishing area, fishing gear, specie, landing information (including utilisation e.g. fishmeal, non-human, Discard, human consumption...) and weight
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data is in an excel file provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available as a whole, but aggregated data can be made available. The report is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data as a whole will not be made openly accessible. Aggregated data extracted by the data will be made available.
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The report is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	

7.2 Appendix 2: Templates

7.2.1 Data Management Plan - Form

1. Data set reference/name	
2. Data summary	
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	
3.2 Making data openly accessible	
3.3 Making data interoperable	
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	
4. Allocation of resources	
5. Data security	
6. Ethical aspects	
7. Other	

7.2.2 Data Management Plan - Explanation

1. Data set reference/name	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identifier for the data set to be produced
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> State the purpose of the data collection/generation, and explain the relation to the objectives of the project Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any) Specify the origin of the data State the expected size of the data (if known) Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision) Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOI)? Outline naming conventions used Outline the approach towards search keyword Outline the approach for clear versioning Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline, describe what type of metadata will be created and how
3.2 Making data openly accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed, explain why Specify how the data will be made available Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)? Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions For a useful registry of possible data repositories, see: https://www.re3data.org/. Search for repositories by subject, content type or country.
3.3 Making data interoperable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability. Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability. If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies? For suggestions on relevant vocabularies, see: http://vest.agrisemantics.org/ For resources on data and metadata standards, see: https://fairsharing.org/
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why Describe data quality assurance processes Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

4. Allocation of resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). Describe how you intend to cover these costs • Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project • Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation
5. Data security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Address procedures for data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data
6. Ethical aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former
7. Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)